

Inheritance of resistance to three endemic viral diseases of cowpea in Nigeria

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Abstract

Mosaic diseases, caused by bean common mosaic virus-blackeye cowpea mosaic strain (BCMV-BICM), southern bean mosaic virus (SBMV) and cucumber mosaic virus (CMV), hamper the productivity of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.). Under single or mixed infections, these endemic viruses significantly reduce cowpea yield in sub-Saharan Africa. Planting resistant varieties is the most effective control method. Knowledge of the mode of inheritance of viral resistance is crucial in developing resistant varieties. Inheritance of resistance to BCMV-BICM, SBMV, and CMV was investigated in two improved cowpea breeding lines. For BCMV-BICM, crosses were made between resistant IT97K-1042-3 (female) and susceptible IT99K-1060 (male); for SBMV, between resistant IT98K-1092-1 (male) and susceptible IT99K-1060 (female); and for CMV, between tolerant IT98K-1092-1 (female) and susceptible IT99K-573-1-1 (male). The F₁ progenies were advanced to F₂ and some F₁ plants were backcrossed to the two parental lines. Reciprocal crosses were made and the seven-day old seedlings of P₁, P₂, F₁, F₂, BCP₁, and BCP₂ were phenotyped by mechanical inoculation with BCMV-BICM, SBMV, and CMV under screenhouse conditions. Data on disease incidence and severity were taken at weekly intervals for five weeks post-inoculation.

26 Virus infections were confirmed via antigen-coated plate enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay
27 or reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction. Chi-square analysis of the genetic
28 segregation indicated that a recessive gene pair in IT97K-1042-3 controlled the inheritance of
29 resistance to BCMV-BICM. Duplicate dominant genes conditioned the resistance to SBMV
30 and tolerance to CMV in IT98K-1092-1. The backcrosses confirmed the monogenic and
31 digenic inheritance patterns, whereas reciprocal crosses indicated absence of cytoplasmic
32 effects.

33 **Keywords:** ACP-ELISA, Cowpea viruses, Epistatic effect, Inheritance pattern, RT-PCR

34 **Introduction**

35 Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.) is one of the most economically and nutritionally
36 important indigenous African grain legumes. It is a diploid species ($2n = 2x = 22$), often self-
37 pollinated, and belongs to the family *Fabaceae* (Boukar et al. 2019). It is the most widely
38 grown and consumed legume in Western Africa (Boukar et al. 2013). Nigeria is the largest
39 producer of cowpea grain, accounting for about 40.9 % of the 8.9 million tons of annual global
40 production (FAOSTAT 2020). Viral diseases remain a significant constraint to cowpea
41 productivity in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) (Thottappilly and Rossel 1992; Legg et al. 2019).
42 Three of the most important seed-transmitted viruses causing significant yield losses in cowpea
43 in SSA are bean common mosaic virus-blackeye cowpea mosaic strain (BCMV–BICM, genus
44 *Potyvirus* family *Potyviridae*); southern bean mosaic virus (SBMV, genus *Sobemovirus*); and
45 cucumber mosaic virus (CMV, genus *Cucumovirus*, family *Bromoviridae*) (Taiwo 2003;
46 Boukar et al. 2019) (Table 1). More serious cowpea grain yield reductions were observed when
47 mixed infections with more than one of these viruses occurred (Boukar et al. 2013). Co-
48 infection of CMV and BCMV-BICM, both transmitted by the same vector, has been reported
49 to produce a synergistic interaction, leading to severe stunting and significant losses in cowpea
50 productivity (Gillaspie, Hajimorad, and Ghabrial 1998; Ogunsoola et al. 2021).

51

52 The use of host-plant resistance is the most economical and environment-friendly option for
53 managing virus diseases (Orawu et al. 2013). Resistance mechanisms in the plant can either
54 block virus replication, interfere with local (cell-to-cell) or vascular (leaf-to-leaf) movement,
55 or/and induce a hypersensitive response (HR) related to programmed cell death (Jones and
56 Dangl 1996). Knowledge of the inheritance pattern of resistance to the virus responsible for
57 causing the disease symptom is essential for the success of a breeding program (Kang, Yeam,
58 and Jahn 2005). Previous studies have identified several resistance (R) genes (Bashir and

59 Hampton 1996; Umaharan, Ariyanayagam, and Haque 1997) and sources of resistance to single
60 and dual viral infections in some cowpea germplasm (Boukar et al. 2013). Although, there are
61 reports on the mode of inheritance of resistance to some viruses infecting cowpea (Taiwo,
62 Provvidenti, and Gonsalves 1981; Orawu et al., 2013), information is still sparse for many of
63 the important cowpea viruses. Moreover, most of the evaluation of sources of virus resistance
64 and inheritance of resistance in cowpea genotypes were limited to field evaluations or virus
65 detection by ELISA, both of which have limitations. For instance, results from field screening
66 under natural infections usually vary because of a lack of control on variables, such as,
67 inoculum source, time of infection and vector activity necessary to ensure uniform infection
68 (Ogunsola et al. 2021). Virus negative results by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay
69 (ELISA), without verification by polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based diagnostics methods,
70 may be inaccurate due to serologically variable strains of viruses or low virus titer undetectable
71 in ELISA but detectable by PCR. (Aliyu, Balogun, and Kumar 2012). This information on the
72 inheritance of virus resistance in cowpea is required in resistance breeding programs because
73 most of the available landraces and commercial cowpea varieties lack durable resistance to the
74 most frequently reported viruses in West Africa (Legg et al. 2019).

75 The genetic bases for resistance to many viral diseases in cowpea are still largely unknown.
76 Understanding the inheritance of resistance to viral diseases of legumes, especially those
77 caused by BCMV-BICM, SBMV, and CMV, is of prime importance for the selection of
78 effective breeding strategy, mating design, and molecular breeding techniques for improved
79 virus-resistant crop varieties (Akbar et al. 2018). A recent study has identified resistance to
80 BCMV-BICM in cowpea line IT97K-1042-3 and both resistance to SBMV and tolerance to
81 CMV in cowpea line IT98K-1092-1 (Table 2) (Ogunsola et al 2021). The line IT90K-284-2, a
82 progenitor of IT97K-1042-3 (Table 2), had also been reported earlier to have a high level of
83 resistance to BCMV-BICM (Bashir et al. 1995). However, the patterns of inheritance to these

84 viruses have not been characterized. This study investigated the inheritance of resistance to
85 mosaic disease caused by BCMV-BICM, SBMV, and CMV in some improved cowpea
86 breeding lines (Table 2). Understanding the genetics of cowpea resistance to viral diseases
87 contributes to developing genomic markers for accelerating the development of improved
88 virus-resistant cowpea varieties.

89

90 **Materials and methods**

91 *Plant materials*

92 Isolates of BCMV-BICM, SBMV, and CMV used were available in the Virology and
93 Molecular Diagnostic (VMD) Unit of IITA, Ibadan. The pure isolates of these viruses were
94 established and maintained by mechanical inoculation onto healthy plants of susceptible
95 cowpea genotypes (Ife Brown, TVu 2657 and TVu 76) in an insect-proof screenhouse. Four
96 improved cowpea breeding lines developed at IITA, namely, IT97K-1042-3 (resistant to
97 BCMV-BICM and SBMV), IT98K-1092-1 (resistant to BCMV-BICM, SBMV and tolerant to
98 CMV), IT99K-573-1-1 (susceptible to BCMV-BICM, CMV and tolerant to SBMV), and
99 IT99K-1060 (susceptible to all three viruses), were used as parental lines (Table 2). Seeds were
100 treated with Benlate fungicide at 1.0 g per 40 seeds. The seeds were sown in 10-inch (25 cm)
101 plastic pots filled with sterilized sandy loam soil and placed in an insect-proof screenhouse.
102 Prostrate and semi-erect plants were staked to enhance crossing.

103

104 *Crossing procedures*

105 The hybridizations were carried out in an insect-proof screenhouse and followed the
106 emasculation and hand-pollination procedure for cowpea described by Myers (1991). Crosses
107 were made between the parental lines resistant (P₁) and susceptible (P₂) to each virus (Tables
108 3, 4, and 5). Floral buds of the female parents that had reached their maximum unopened size

109 (a day prior to opening) were carefully emasculated by making approximately 4.0 mm cut on
110 the concave part of the unopened flower. The upper part of the cut segment was lifted with
111 forceps, exposing the style and stamens, and anthers were carefully removed. Flowers that
112 opened on male parents were plucked and their pollen dusted by rubbing the anthers on the
113 stigma and hairy segment of the style of emasculated flowers of the female parent plants.
114 Labeled tags were carefully fixed to the base of the pollinated female flowers to develop to pod
115 maturity.

116

117 The BCMV-BICM resistant line IT97K-1042-3 (female parent) was crossed with the
118 susceptible IT99K-1060. The F₁ plants were advanced to F₂, whereas the former was
119 backcrossed to each of the two parents to generate BCP₁ and BCP₂ (Table 3). An SBMV-
120 resistant line IT98K-1092-1 was crossed to the susceptible line IT99K-1060 (Table 4).
121 However, in this case, the resistant line was used as a male parent because of the very low rate
122 of successful crosses when the resistant line was used as a female parent. Some of the F₁ plants
123 were advanced to F₂ and also backcrossed to the two parents to produce BCP₁ and BCP₂
124 generations (Table 4). The CMV-tolerant cowpea line IT98K-1092-1 (female parent) and
125 susceptible line IT99K-573-1-1 were crossed reciprocally, and the F₁ progeny was advanced
126 to F₂, using some of them to generate backcrosses BCP₁ and BCP₂ (Table 5). Mature pods of
127 the generations P₁, P₂, F₁, F₂, BCP₁ and BCP₂ from each cross were harvested, dried in the
128 screenhouse, shelled and seeds were stored at 4⁰C until planting for virus resistance screening.

129

130 ***Evaluation of cowpea generations for reactions to viruses***

131 Seeds of P₁, P₂, F₁, F₂, BCP₁, and BCP₂ were planted at a rate of two seeds per pot in an insect-
132 proof screenhouse. Seedlings from the crosses were tested to confirm successful hybridization
133 based on traits like shape, length and width of the terminal leaflets, length of internodes, pod

134 length and shape of the plants compared to the parental lines. Seedlings were mechanically
135 inoculated with BCMV-BICM, SBMV, or CMV according to the parents crossed. Virus
136 inoculum was prepared by grinding virus-infected cowpea leaves in a pre-chilled sterilized
137 mortar in 1:10 (w/v) ratio in 0.05 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.5, containing 0.04% (v/v) β -
138 mercaptoethanol. Inoculation was carried out by dusting carborundum (600 mesh) on the
139 primary leaves of six- to eight-day-old seedlings to create micro-wounds and freshly prepared
140 inoculum of each virus was applied on respective test plants. Each population was screened on
141 an individual plant basis, with each pot well labeled to identify each plant. Sixteen Ife brown
142 plants were raised and inoculated as a positive control, whereas ten plants of each parental line
143 were used as healthy control.

144

145 ***Virus detection using ACP-ELISA***

146 Five weeks after inoculation (WAI), all plants were tested for BCMV-BICM, SBMV or CMV
147 based on the type of virus under study. Antigen Coated Plate-Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent
148 Assay (ACP-ELISA) containing homologous anti-rabbit antibodies to each virus available at
149 the Virology and Molecular Diagnostics Unit of IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria, were used (Kumar et
150 al. 2001). About 100 mg of tissue from the leaf apex of each plant was used for virus testing in
151 a 96-well NUNC MaxiSorb (Nunc, Denmark) ELISA plate. Alkaline phosphatase (ALP)-
152 labeled anti-rabbit antibodies were used to detect the immobilized antigen-antibody complex
153 and p-nitrophenyl phosphate (Sigma, Gillingham, UK) was used as substrate. After 1 h of
154 incubation, absorbance readings were taken at 405 nm (A405 nm) in a Multiscan Plus ELISA
155 plate reader (Labsystems, Helsinki, Finland). Sample with A405 nm value of at least twice (2x
156 and above) that of the healthy control was considered positive to the virus. Samples that tested
157 negative with ELISA were verified by retesting samples with Reverse Transcription-

158 Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-PCR) using the primer pair corresponding to the respective
159 viruses according to Kumar (2009).

160

161 ***Virus detection by RT-PCR***

162 Total RNA was isolated from the apical leaf tissues (100 mg) according to a modified
163 cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) method (Abarshi et al. 2010) and used for
164 detection of BCMV-BICM, SBMV and CMV by RT-PCR according to the procedure described
165 by Kumar (2009). BCMV-BICM amplification was performed using the primer pair, CI-F,
166 CGIVIGTIGGIWSIGGIAARTCIAC and CI-R, ACICCRTTYTCDATDATRTTIGTIGC,
167 which amplifies 700 bp segment (Kumar, 2009). SBMV was detected using the primer pair,
168 SBMV-F, TGGTCCTTCGACGCAATCT and SBMV-R, GTCTGCTTCAGCTGCAGGACA,
169 which amplifies 500 bp segment (Salem et al., 2010) and CMV was detected using the primer
170 pair CMV-F, GCCGTAAGCTGGATGGACAA and CMV-R, TATGATAAGAAGCTTGTT
171 TCGCG, which amplifies 500 bp segment (Wylie et al., 1993). PCR amplification was
172 performed in 12.5- μ l reaction mixture comprising 10x PCR reaction buffer (supplied with Taq
173 enzyme), 0.75 μ l of 25 mM MgCl₂, 0.25 μ l mixture of 10 mM deoxynucleotide triphosphates,
174 0.25 μ l of respective primers, 12 units of Molony-murine leukemia virus (M-MLV) reverse
175 transcriptase (RT) (Promega Corporation, USA), 0.3 units of Taq DNA polymerase (Promega
176 Corporation, Madison, Wisconsin, USA), and 2.0 μ l of 10 ng/ μ l total RNA and sterile distilled
177 water. Virus RNAs were amplified with Applied Biosystems (GeneAmp® PCR System 9700)
178 Cyclor machine. Amplification of BCMV-BICM RNA was done as follows: one cycle for 30
179 min at 42°C, and 35 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 30 sec, primer annealing at 40°C for 30
180 sec, extension at 68°C for 1 min and final extension at 72°C for 10 min. Similar thermal cyclor
181 conditions was used to detect SBMV and CMV except that annealing temperatures were 54°C

182 and 50°C, respectively, for SBMV and CMV. Amplified RT-PCR products were separated in
183 1% agarose gel electrophoresis in 0.5 x TBE buffer and visualized under UV transilluminator
184 (BioRad) after staining in ethidium bromide (0.5 µg/ml).

185

186 ***Classification of test plants based on visual rating, serology, and molecular diagnostics***

187 Viral disease incidence was determined using the ratio of the number of symptomatic to the
188 total number of inoculated plants. Disease severity was determined by taking weekly symptom
189 severity scores from the period of one-week after inoculation (WAI) to 5 WAI. Severity scale
190 1-5 was used, where 1= no visible symptom, 2= very mild mosaic or mottling on few leaves,
191 3= mosaic or mottling on many leaves, 4= severe mosaic, severe mottling, and mild stunting
192 and 5= severe mosaic, severe mottling, severe stunting with necrosis or death of leaves and/or
193 plants (Ogunsola et al. 2021). Inoculated test plants in the different populations were classified
194 as resistant, tolerant, or susceptible based on symptom severity scores, and diagnostic
195 confirmation for the presence or absence of virus done via ACP-ELISA and/or RT-PCR. Plants
196 without symptoms (severity score 1) and virus-negative in diagnostic test were classified as
197 resistant (R). Plants with severity score of between >1 and 2 (mild mosaic or mottling without
198 reduction in growth and vigor) and test positive for virus were classified as tolerant (T). Plants
199 with severity score of 3, 4, and 5 and positive to virus in the diagnostics test were classified as
200 susceptible (Ogunsola et al. 2021).

201

202 ***Data analysis***

203 Plants of P₁, P₂, F₁, F₂, BCP₁ and BCP₂ generations of each cross were classified into resistant
204 or susceptible to BCMV-BICM, SBMV, and tolerant or susceptible to CMV. Data of the F₂,
205 BCP₁ and BCP₂ individuals in the direct and reciprocal crosses, scored as resistant/tolerant or

206 susceptible, were subjected to Chi-square (χ^2) analysis for goodness-of-fit to test the deviation
207 of the observed segregation data from the theoretically expected Mendelian segregation ratio.
208 The comparison between the observed and expected frequencies was used to determine the
209 patterns of inheritance and estimate the number of genes controlling resistance/ tolerance, using
210 χ^2 analysis as per the formula of Gomez and Gomez (1984) given as: $\chi^2 = \sum (O - E)^2 / E$
211 where O = observed number of individuals and E = expected number of individuals

212

213 **Results**

214 *Inheritance of resistance to BCMV–BICM disease in cowpea*

215 Evaluation of the parental lines, and F₁, F₂, BCP₁ and BCP₂ generations for resistance to
216 BCMV–BICM showed that all inoculated plants of line IT97K-1042-3 were symptomless
217 (Figure 1 (A1)), negative to ACP-ELISA, and confirmed negative by RT-PCR (Figure 2 (A)).
218 The susceptible parental plants (IT99K-1060) developed systemic symptoms characteristic of
219 BCMV–BICM (Figure 1 (A3)) and tested positive for BCMV–BICM via ELISA and RT-PCR
220 (Figure 2 (A2)). Symptom expression started with mild mosaic and mottling, which progressed
221 into mosaic and vein banding with the aging of plants. The F₁ plants developed symptoms
222 similar to that of the susceptible parent (Figure 1 (A2)), suggesting that resistance to BCMV–
223 BICM was recessive. Plants of F₂ generation responded to virus inoculation with some
224 symptomless plants that tested negative in ELISA and RT-PCR, whereas others showed mild
225 or severe symptoms (Figure 1 (A4)). Evaluation of the F₂ plants for resistance to BCMV–BICM
226 showed 72 resistant and 251 susceptible plants (Table 3). The segregation pattern by Chi-
227 square (χ^2) test gave a goodness-of-fit of 1 resistant: 3 susceptible, which indicates that a single
228 recessive gene pair conditions the resistance to BCMV–BICM in IT97K-1042-3. Symptoms
229 observed on most of the symptomatic backcross generation plants were not severe (Figure 1
230 (A5 and A6)). Plants resulting from backcross to the susceptible parent (BCP₂) were all

231 symptomatic, indicating that they were susceptible, whereas those from backcross to the
232 resistant parent (BCP₁) segregated into 18 resistant: 20 susceptible. This fitted a ratio of 1
233 resistant: 1 susceptible ($p > 0.05$). These results of the backcross generations confirmed the
234 monogenic inheritance of resistance to BCMV-BICM (Table 3) in cowpea line IT97K-1042-3.
235 The F₂ generation that resulted from a reciprocal cross between the same parents gave 157
236 susceptible to 69 resistant plants, which fitted a segregation ratio of 3 susceptible to 1 resistant
237 plant (Table 3). Evaluation of the backcross to resistant parent also resulted in 15 susceptible
238 to 19 resistant plants, which gave a goodness-of-fit to 1 susceptible: 1 resistant segregation
239 ratio, indicating the absence of maternal or cytoplasmic inheritance.

240

241 ***Inheritance of resistance to SBMV disease in cowpea***

242 Symptoms developed on susceptible parental plants of line IT99K-1060 (P₁) following
243 inoculation with SBMV (Figure 1 (B1)). Serological analysis using ACP-ELISA confirmed the
244 presence of the virus in the plants, whereas P₂ plants were asymptomatic (Figure 1 (B3)) and
245 negative when tested by ELISA and RT-PCR (Figure 2 (B)). All the F₁ plants evaluated showed
246 resistance to SBMV infection, suggesting the dominance of resistance to SBMV in parent
247 IT98K-1092-1. Visual evaluation and diagnostic test of F₂ generation plants revealed 207
248 resistant and 18 susceptible, which when subjected to Chi-square analysis ($p > 0.05$) fitted a
249 segregation ratio of 15 resistant:1 susceptible (Table 4). This indicated an epistatic effect of
250 two dominant genes in duplicate gene action. The backcross to the susceptible parent showed
251 segregation of 26 resistant: 9 susceptible plants, which fitted the 3 resistant: 1 susceptible ratio.
252 This suggested that duplicate dominant genes conditioned the resistance of IT99K 1092-1 to
253 SBMV.

254

255 ***Inheritance of tolerance to CMV disease in cowpea***

256 When inoculated with CMV, some of the tolerant parent plants (IT98K-1092-1) did not
257 produce visible symptoms, whereas others showed mild symptoms (severity scores >1 to 2) of
258 mottling and inter-veinal chlorosis but without puckering (Figure 1 (C1)). The susceptible
259 parent plants (IT99K-573-1-1) inoculated with CMV produced visible symptoms of mottling,
260 mosaic, inter-veinal chlorosis, and puckering, which began to appear eight days after
261 inoculation (Figure 1 (C3)). Symptom expression was obvious in all susceptible plants (severity
262 scores 3 to 4). Both tolerant and susceptible parental lines and F₁, F₂, BCP₁, and BCP₂
263 generations tested positive for CMV using ACP-ELISA and RT-PCR (Figure 2 (C)).
264 Meanwhile, symptoms faded in some CMV symptomatic plants, starting from four weeks after
265 inoculation, although such plants remained positive for CMV via the ELISA test. The F₁ plants
266 derived from the cross between tolerant and susceptible lines when inoculated with CMV
267 showed reactions similar to that of the tolerant parent, in which some plants were symptomless,
268 whereas others showed mild symptoms (Figure 1 (C2)). This suggested that the tolerance of
269 line IT99K-1092-1 to CMV was a dominant trait. Following the visual observation, the F₂
270 generation segregated 264 tolerant: 25 susceptible plants, which gave a goodness-of-fit to 15
271 tolerant: 1 susceptible segregation ratio (Table 5). The segregation ratio of 3:1 tolerant:
272 susceptible plants (25 tolerant: 7 susceptible plants) obtained from the backcross to the
273 susceptible parent supported the digenic inheritance of tolerance to CMV (the expected
274 backcross ratio 1:1:1:1 of a dihybrid cross modified into 3:1 tolerant to susceptible plants due
275 to the duplicate dominant epistatic gene action). Reciprocal crosses between the same parental
276 lines gave similar segregation ratios of 15 tolerant: 1 susceptible in the F₂ generation, indicating
277 the absence of extrachromosomal (maternal) inheritance (Table 5).

278

279

280

281 **Discussion**

282 In this study, analyses of F₁, F₂, backcrosses, and reciprocal crosses between resistant and
283 susceptible lines indicated that resistance to BCMV-BICM in cowpea line IT97K-1042-3 was
284 controlled by a recessive gene pair, with no maternal effects. Previous studies on BCMV-BICM
285 resistance in cowpea suggested diverse mechanisms with respect to the mode of inheritance.
286 Single recessive genes were reported to be responsible for resistance to the virus by Arshad et
287 al. (1998) and Taiwo, Provvidenti, and Gonsalves (1981). In contrast, Quatara and Chambliss
288 (1991) observed a single dominant gene-controlled resistance to this virus in cowpea. Similar
289 results of a single dominant gene conditioning the resistance to BCMV-BICM were reported
290 in common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) and cowpea (Provvidenti, Gonslaves, and Taiwo 1983;
291 Sharma et al. 2008).

292

293 Unlike the previous studies, which were based on the identification of resistant plants using
294 only symptom expression and serological detection, the PCR-based detection method used in
295 this study increased the accuracy of the classification of infected cowpea populations into
296 resistant and susceptible plants. Meanwhile, the single dominant resistance gene reported in
297 cowpea cultivar “White Acre-BVR” by Quatara and Chambliss (1991) is different from that
298 found in the present study. A combination of the two genes in a cowpea variety should confer
299 more durable resistance to BCMV-BICM than if either gene is used as a source of resistance.
300 Should any of the two genes break down due to the development of a new mutant virus, the
301 other gene would still confer resistance to the virus. The possibility of a breakdown of
302 resistance gene in cowpea has been observed with the single dominant gene (*Rac*) (Bata et al.
303 1987) in germplasm line TVu3000 (Boukar et al. 2020) that was used to confer resistance to
304 aphids in the seedling stage of plant development.

305

306 Crosses between the SBMV-resistant line IT98K-1092-1 and susceptible line IT99K-1060
307 could not be made when the former was used as a female parent. The F₁ and segregating
308 populations (F₂, BCP₁ and BCP₂) derived from the cross between IT98K-1092-1 and IT99K-
309 1060 were evaluated for their reactions to the virus. Chi-square analysis of the F₁, F₂, BCP₁
310 and BCP₂ populations showed that duplicate dominant genes with an epistatic interaction
311 conditioned the inheritance of resistance to SBMV in the cowpea line IT98K-1092-1. Brantley
312 and Kuhn (1970) and Fery (1980) have earlier reported dominance of resistance to SBMV in
313 cowpea controlled by a single gene. Furthermore, the inheritance pattern of non-necrotic
314 resistance to SBMV in cowpea was cultivar-dependent. A cross between an SBMV-susceptible
315 line “California Blackeye” and three resistant cowpea lines showed that SBMV resistance in
316 cultivar “Early Pinkeye and “PI 18646” was conferred by a single gene with partial dominance,
317 whereas that in “Iron,” the third variety, was attributable to multiple genes with incomplete
318 dominance (Hobbs et al. 1987).

319

320 The symptoms induced by SBMV are reported to be variable among cowpea lines, ranging
321 from asymptomatic lines to those showing severe mosaic, with deformed leaves (Kuhn 1990).
322 Being seed-borne, SBMV has become widely distributed across several countries where
323 cowpea is grown (Thottappilly and Rossel, 1992). This is a further reason why concerted efforts
324 should be made to develop improved cowpea varieties with resistance to this virus. The
325 detection of the line with resistance to the virus controlled by duplicate dominant genes with
326 epistatic effects should enable the successful development of resistant varieties.

327

328 In the case of CMV, only a tolerant cowpea line (IT98K-1092-1) was detected. The absence of
329 symptoms by some of the CMV-tolerant plants might be due to the already reported latency of
330 the virus in IT98K-1092-1 (Ogunsola et al. 2021). The F₁, F₂, BCP₁, and BCP₂ resulting from

331 the cross between IT98K-1092-1 and susceptible IT99K-573-1-1 showed F₁ plants to be
332 tolerant. This is evidence that tolerance in line IT98K-1092-1 is dominant to susceptibility. The
333 F₂ and backcross generations confirmed that tolerance to CMV in the cowpea line IT98K-1092-
334 1 was governed by duplicate dominant genes, with the absence of maternal or extra-
335 chromosomal factors. Reports on the mode of inheritance of tolerance to CMV are limited in
336 cowpea. The CMV, which is seed-borne and transmitted by aphids, is considered to have mild
337 effects on the crop under a single infection (Pio-Ribeiro, Kuhn, and Brantley 1980) but causes
338 severe symptoms in the case of mixed infection with other viruses (Ogunsola et al. 2021). It is
339 however, widespread in distribution. In view of the presently available knowledge on the
340 genome of this virus, CMV-mediated transgenic resistance is feasible as a means of controlling
341 the disease in cowpea (Hampton et al., 1997).

342

343 The non-parametric Chi-square analysis for testing the goodness-of-fit to simple genetic model
344 has been used in several studies to investigate the mode of inheritance of resistance to viral
345 diseases of cowpea (Quatara and Chambliss 1991; Arshad et al. 1998; Orawu et al. 2013; Silva
346 et al. 2021) and many other legumes (Ogundiwin et al. 2002; Sharma et al. 2008). Monogenic
347 (Quatara and Chambliss 1991; Silva et al. 2021) or digenic inheritance (Barro et al. 2016) of
348 virus resistance were mostly reported in cowpea and other legumes. However, in some cases,
349 viral diseases of cowpea were observed to be quantitatively inherited (Orawu et al. 2013).
350 Investigating quantitative inheritance is usually carried out using combining ability estimates
351 of cowpea lines or a generation mean analysis (Akbar et al. 2018). In addition, studies involving
352 both quantitative and qualitative analyses of resistance to viruses in cowpea have been reported.
353 For instance, cowpea aphid-borne mosaic virus (CABMV) resistance was reported to be
354 conditioned by a single recessive gene in seven cowpea populations and more than one

355 recessive gene in other eight populations, in which both additive and non-additive gene actions
356 were indicated for the virus resistance (Orawu et al. 2013).

357

358 Most of the reported studies on the inheritance of resistance to BCMV-BICM (Taiwo,
359 Provvidenti, and Gonsalves 1981; Quatara and Chambliss 1991; Arshad et al. 1998) and SBMV
360 (Hobbs et al. 1987) in cowpea were based on plant virus assessment by symptomatology and
361 ELISA. When not validated by molecular diagnosis, both methods might impair the accuracy
362 of the observed classes of the segregating plant populations categorized into resistant or
363 susceptible plants.

364

365 Recently, BCMV-BICM, SBMV, and CMV have been reported to be among the most
366 important cowpea-infecting viruses in SSA (Legg et al. 2019; Kumar et al. 2021). Knowledge
367 of patterns of inheritance of resistance and tolerance to the viruses in cowpea varieties found
368 here should help plant breeders and virologists develop breeding strategies that will provide
369 effective and stable disease management. Though there is a higher likelihood of breakdown of
370 monogenic resistance following the evolution of new virulent strains with time than the
371 resistance conditioned by polygenes (Arshad et al. 1998), monogenic resistance is not always
372 unstable in edible legumes. For instance, monogenic resistance to BCMV was observed in
373 common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) for nearly half a century. Resistance to anthracnose in the
374 same crop lasted for almost 20 years. It was only in a few diseases of legumes, such as bean
375 rust and lima bean downy mildew, where monogenic resistance was for a short duration
376 (Meiners 1981). It is easier and faster to transfer monogenic than multigenic resistance to other
377 desired cultivars (Arshad et al. 1998) since the use of monogenic resistance requires fewer
378 resources. The monogenic inheritance of BCMV-BICM resistance and digenic nature of
379 inheritance of resistance and tolerance to SBMV and CMV, respectively, as observed in this

380 study, can enhance ease of transfer of the viral R genes from the identified resistant lines in
381 developing virus-resistant cowpea varieties. The genomic resources generated in cowpea can
382 be explored to facilitate progress in the development of varieties with resistance to these and
383 other disease-causing organisms.

384

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391

392 **Author Contributions**

393 The study was conceived, designed and supervised by PL Kumar and CA Fatokun. KE
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Table 1. Properties of bean common mosaic virus-blackeye cowpea mosaic strain (BCMV-BICM), southern bean mosaic virus (SBMV) and cucumber mosaic virus (CMV) infecting cowpea

Virus	Genus	Insect transmission		Symptom [†]	Yield loss (%)	Reference
		vector	mode			
BCMV-BICM	Potyvirus	Aphid	Non-persistent	M, Mo, Vb, Vc	54 - 74	Udayashankar et al. (2010); Jordan and Hammond (2008)
SBMV	Sobemovirus	Leaf beetles	Non-persistent	M, Vc, NI, Ld	11 - 59	Givord (1981); Karim (2016)
CMV	Cucumovirus	Aphid	Non-persistent	M, Mo, Cl, Ld	14 - 20	Zitter and Murphy (2009)

[†]M = mosaic, Mo = mottling, Vb = vein banding, Vc = vein clearing, NI = necrotic lesion, Ld = leaf distortion, Cl = Chlorotic lesion.

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Table 2 Characteristics of cowpea genotypes evaluated

Genotypes	Response [†]	Seed coat colour	Growth [‡] habit	Maturity	Pedigree
IT98K-1092-1	Resistant to BCMV-BICM, and SBMV but tolerant to CMV	Black	S.E	Medium	IT93K-596 x TVu 12349
IT97K-1042-3	Resistant to BCMV-BICM and SBMV but susceptible to CMV	Brown	E	Early	IT90K-284 x Achishiru-2
IT99K-573-1-1	Susceptible to BCMV-BICM, CMV but tolerant to SBMV	White	P	Medium	IT93K-596-6-12 x IT86D-880
IT99K-1060	Susceptible to BCMV-BICM, SBMV and CMV	Brown	E	Early	unknown

Source: Cowpea Breeding Unit, IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria

[†]Cowpea response to viral infections (Ogunsola et al. 2021)

[‡]S.E, Semi-erect; E, Erect; P, Prostrate

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Table 3. Inheritance of resistance to bean common mosaic virus (BCMV-BICM) in cowpea

Generations and crosses	No of plants [§]			Expected Ratio	χ^2	Probability	BCMV-BICM resistance gene action
	R	S	Total				
Resistant parent (R) IT97K-1042-3 (aa) [†]	30	-	30				Recessive
Susceptible parent (S) IT99K-1060 (AA) [‡]	-	35	35				Dominant
F ₁ (R x S) (aa x AA)	-	33	33				Recessive resistance
F ₂	72	251	323	3:1	1.278	0.30 - 0.20	Monogenic recessive
Backcrosses							
BCP ₁ (R x F ₁)	18	20	38	1:1	0.106	0.80 - 0.70	Monogenic recessive
BCP ₂ (S x F ₁)	-	26	26	-	-	-	
Reciprocal cross							
F ₁ (S x R) (AA x aa)	-	28	28				Monogenic recessive
F ₂	69	157	226	3:1	3.687	0.10 - 0.05	
Backcrosses							
BCP ₁ (S x F ₁)	-	38	38	-	-	-	
BCP ₂ (R x F ₁)	19	15	34	1:1	0.471	0.50 - 0.40	

[†]aa = line with recessive trait

[‡]AA = line with dominant trait

[§]R = resistant plants, S = susceptible plants

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Table 4. Inheritance of resistance to southern bean mosaic virus (SBMV) in cowpea

Generations and crosses	No of plants [§]			Expected Ratio	χ^2	Probability	SBMV resistance gene action
	R	S	Total				
Susceptible parent (S)							
IT99K-1060 (aabb) [†]	-	28	28				Recessive
Resistant parent (R)							
IT98K-1092-1 (AABB) [‡]	40	-	40				Dominant
F ₁ (S x R) (aabb x AABB)	45		45				Dominant resistance
F ₂	207	18	225	15. 1	1.178	0.30 - 0.20	Duplicate dominant
Backcrosses							
BCP ₁ (S x F ₁)	26	9	35	3. 1	0.009	0.95 - 0.90	Duplicate dominant
BCP ₂ (R x F ₁)	36		36	-	-	-	-

[†]aabb = Line with recessive trait

[‡]AABB = Line with dominant trait

[§]R = resistant plants, S = susceptible plants

Table 5. Inheritance of tolerance to cucumber mosaic virus (CMV) in cowpea

Generations and crosses	No of plants [§]			Expected ratio	χ^2	Probability	CMV tolerance gene action
	T	S	Total				
Tolerant parent (T)							
IT98K-1092-1 (AABB) [†]	23	-	23				Dominant
Susceptible parent (S)							
IT99K-573-1-1 (aabb) [‡]	-	36	36				Recessive
F ₁ (T x S) (AABB x aabb)	23	-	23				Dominant tolerance
F ₂	264	25	289	15.1	2.845	0.10 - 0.05	Duplicate dominant
Backcrosses							
BCP ₁ (T x F ₁)	16	-	16	-	-	-	
BCP ₂ (S x F ₁)	25	7	32	3.1	0.167	0.70 - 0.60	Duplicate dominant
Reciprocal crosses							
F ₁ (S x T) (aabb x AABB)	13	-	13				Duplicate dominant
F ₂	166	16	182	15.1	2.005	0.20 - 0.10	
Backcrosses							
BCP ₁ (S x F ₁)	13	5	18	3.1	0.075	0.80 - 0.70	
BCP ₂ (T x F ₁)	18	-	18	-	-	-	

[†]AABB = Line with dominant trait

[‡]aabb = Line with recessive trait

[§]T = tolerant plants, S = susceptible plants

Figure 1 (A - C). P₁, F₁, P₂, F₂, BCP₁ and BCP₂ generations of direct crosses between (A) BCMV-BICM (B) SBMA and (C) CMV resistant (R), tolerant (T) or susceptible (S) cowpea lines. (A1) P₁, BCMV-BICM resistant male parent: IT97K-1042-3; (A2) F₁ (R x S); (A3) P₂, BCMV-BICM susceptible female parent: IT99K-1060; (A4) F₂; (A5) BCP₁ (R x F₁); (A6) BCP₂ (S x F₁); (B1) P₁, SBMV susceptible female parent: IT99K-1060; (B2) F₁ (S x R); (B3) P₂, SBMV resistant male parent: IT98K-1092-1; (B4) F₂; (B5) BCP₁ (S x F₁); (B6) BCP₂ (R x F₁); (C1) P₁, CMV tolerant: IT98K-1092-12; (C2) F₁ (T x S); (C3) CMV P₂, CMV susceptible: IT99K-573-1-1; (C4) F₂; (C5) BCP₁ (T x F₁); (C6) BCP₂ (S x F₁). A = BCMV-BICM, B = SBMV and C = CMV

Figure 2 (A - C) Detection or lack of detection of (A) BCMV-BICM, (B) SBMV and (C) CMV in cowpea by RT-PCR; M, DNA size marker (100 bp ladder; Promega); lanes 1 - 4, 1 -8 and 1-13 = extracts of plant samples (A = samples with no detection of BCMV-BICM, A2 = BCMV-BICM infected samples; B = samples with no detection of SBMV and B2 = SBMV infected samples; C = CMV infected samples); n, uninfected cowpea sample; b = no template control; p = virus positive control.